

Minutes of the 53rd Experimenters' Meeting

The Cosener's House, Abingdon, Thursday 10th July 2014

(This document was finalised on 29th August 2014)

Present:

Mrs Lizzy Dyson ²	(LJD)	
Dr Jon Eastment ^{3,4}	(JDE)	
Dr Catherine Gaffard ²	(CG)	
Dr David Hooper ^{3,4}	(DAH)	Secretary
Dr Sian Lane ²	(SEL)	
Dr Chris Lee ⁶	(CFL)	
Dr Zhihong Li ²	(ZL)	
Dr Graham Parton ^{1,4}	(GAP)	
Dr Jeremy Price ²	(JP)	
Dr Hugo Ricketts ⁵	(HMAR)	
Mr Jim Trice ²	(JMT)	
Prof Geraint Vaughan ⁵	(GV)	Chair
Dr Chris Walden ⁴	(CJW)	

Affiliation:

¹British Atmospheric Data Centre (BADC)

²Met Office

³NERC MST Radar Facility

⁴Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL)

⁵University of Manchester

⁶University of Reading

Abbreviations used in this document:

BL(WP)	Boundary-Layer (Wind-Profiler)
DK	Dirk Klugmann (former manager of the Met Office's Upper Air Sensing Team)
EGN	Emily Norton (University of Manchester)
EUCOS	EUMETNET Composite Observing System
FSO	Forecast Sensitivity to Observations
HAARP	High Frequency Active Auroral Research Program
LCBR	Laser Cloud Base Recorder
LD	Les Dean (MSTRF site technician)
MST(R)(F)	Mesosphere-Stratosphere-Troposphere (Radar) (Facility)
NCAS	National Centre for Atmospheric Science
NERC	Natural Environment Research Council
NLC	Noctilucent Cloud
NWP	Numerical Weather Prediction
PC	Personal Computer
RMS	Root Mean Square
TX	Transmitter
UPS	Uninterruptable Power Supply
UT	Universal Time

1. Minutes of the previous meeting

GV pointed out that the reference to the “harpar.dat” file in the 2nd paragraph of section 5a (page 6) was slightly incorrect. It should have been “hardpar.dat”.

2. Matters arising

ACTION ITEM 46.5.3 GAP and DK to investigate the possibility of storing data from all of the Met Office’s new Jenoptik Laser Cloud Base Recorder (LCBR) on the BADC.

ONGOING

GAP reported that he hoped to make significant progress on this when he visits the Met Office in August 2014. JMT reported that the “lidarnet” network, into which LCBR data are fed, is in the process of transition. He also reported that DK has now left the Met Office. DK’s responsibilities are being split between two other managers until a new person is recruited to fill his position.

ACTION ITEM 51.6.1 DAH to determine an improved method of applying the horizontal wind θ_s compensation factor so that its contribution to random errors is minimised.

ONGOING

DAH will give an update on this work in section 6f. He will not devote any time to the following three action items (47.2.1, 47.2.2, and 47.3.2) until 51.6.1 has been completed.

ACTION ITEM 47.2.1 DAH to modify the MST radar signal processing software, as soon as possible, to allow it to make use of updated Python programming libraries.

ONGOING

ACTION ITEM 47.2.2 DAH to ensure, as soon as possible, that MST radar data products generated by the latest version of the signal processing software are available for the entire observation archive.

ONGOING

ACTION ITEM 47.3.2 DAH to recreate cloud base altitude files, starting from 2nd November 2010, with the time stamps corrected.

ONGOING

ACTION ITEM 48.4.2 DAH and JDE to investigate the opportunities for returning the spare MST radar transmitter to working order.

COMPLETED

DAH and JDE reported that although, in principle, the spare transmitter could be repaired, this would be a task-consuming task. A better long-term strategy would be to replace all of the transmitters. The current units are 25 years old and rely on components that are no longer manufactured. It will become increasingly difficult to maintain them. Consequently DAH and JDE are interested in the performance of the Met Office’s South Uist radar, which has recently been renovated and is now powered by a modern, solid-state transmitter. This led to the creation of the following two new action items.

ACTION ITEM 53.2.1 JMT and LJD to report at the next meeting on the effects of the recent renovation on the South Uist radar and on the performance of its new transmitter.

NEW

ACTION ITEM 53.2.2 DAH and JDE to develop a business case for replacing the NERC MST Radar's transmitters with modern, solid-state units.

NEW

ACTION ITEM 50.5.1 EGN to liaise with GAP in order to sort out the archiving of BLWP data on the BADC.

COMPLETED

GAP reported that all of the raw data files are now in the BADC, although the coverage for processed data files is patchy. He aims to soon issue digital object identifiers (DOIs) for each campaign dataset and for long term observational periods.

ACTION ITEM 51.4.1 DAH to increase the storage capacity of the Frongoch data logger so that communications failures do not lead to data loss.

ONGOING

DAH reported that in order to carry out this one task, he will be obliged to carry out a number of connected tasks simultaneously. For example he will need to replace both the Frongoch and Capel Dewi data loggers, write data acquisition software for the new units, and install a new PC for the data download software. Consequently this action remains a secondary priority until 51.6.1 has been completed.

ACTION ITEM 51.4.2 DAH to make the Met Office's model-comparison statistics for the MST radar permanently available to users if the Met Office will allow this.

ONGOING

LJD reported that she has now taken over from David Edwards as the primary point of contact for wind-profiler issues at the Met Office.

Referring to the last sentence in section 3 of the previous meeting's minutes, GV asked that his "recommendation" be upgraded to an action item.

ACTION ITEM 53.2.3 DAH and JDE to introduce procedures so that someone at RAL will monitor the operation of the MST Radar for periods when DAH is on leave.

NEW

3. Facility Report - DAH

3a) Transfer Of Facility to NCAS

DAH reported that responsibility for NERC's atmospheric radar facilities - the MSTRF, the Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research (CFARR), and the UK support for the European Incoherent Scatter Scientific Association (EISCAT) - had been transferred from NERC's Service's and Facilities team to NCAS on 1st April 2014. GV, in his capacity as NCAS Director of Observations, will be in charge. In principle these changes should not have any effect on user scientists' interactions with the

facilities.

3b) Data Management

GAP reported that the BADC is in the process of migrating its data delivery system. However, this should have no impact on user scientists' access to the files.

GAP has analysed the BADC's MSTRF data download statistics for the past year. The number of people who have accessed the data (26) is approximately three times the number of registered users (9). This is important to know since the number of applications for facility support has dropped off significantly since the dataset became open-access.

ACTION ITEM 53.3.1 GAP to provide DAH with further details of the use of MSTRF data by people who are not registered users.

NEW

3c) Electricity

The Uninterruptable Power Supply (UPS) units had to switch battery power briefly (i.e. for no more than a few seconds at a time) on 29 occasions between late November 2013 and early July 2014. Sixteen of these occurred on 12th February 2014, when the strong surface winds are likely to have been the cause of the disruptions. On a further 8 occasions, since late November 2013, the UPS units switched to battery power for between 3 and 30 s at a time. Two longer interruptions occurred on 3rd March 2014, the first lasting for 4 minutes and the second for 11 minutes. On the second occasion the UPS unit for one of the transmitters (TXA) indicated that it was so low on energy that it would have to shut down imminently. However, it appears that the mains power resumed before this became necessary.

3d) Telecommunications

The MSTRF's internet connection was out of action between 31st December 2013 and 9th January 2014. This was the result of a fault on the section of phone line immediately outside of the site. DAH had successfully re-established a lost connection on 28th December by remotely power-cycling the router. However, although it was not apparent at the time, the resulting speed was low and the large spectral files failed to be uploaded to the BADC. After the connection went down again on the evening of 31st December DAH was not able to re-establish it for long enough to be of any use. LD visited the site on 2nd January and transferred the MSTRF's router on to the phone line used for the University of Manchester's internet connection (which relies on the same service provider). This ensured that real-time wind-profile data could be sent to the Met Office for the week remaining before the MSTRF's line was repaired.

The MSTRF's broadband router failed on the afternoon of Saturday 25th January 2014. This coincided with the passage of a deep convective system over the site and so it is possible that nearby lightning activity might have been responsible. LD visited the site on the following day and re-established the connection by switching to the backup router. DAH installed a new router on 26th March 2014. The new unit has not dropped a connection so far. It's not clear whether this is because it is more robust than the previous one (both DrayTek Vigor2830 series ADSL Router Firewall models) or because there have been fewer underlying problems on the line.

The phone line used by the fire alarm system developed a fault around 14th March 2014. The source of the problem was traced to a location external to the site. The University of Manchester's internet connection developed a problem around 14th April 2014. However, this turned out to be caused by their router.

3e) Anti-Geo-Engineering Protest

The MST Radar was the target of an anti-geo-engineering protest over the weekend of 21st/22nd June 2014. The reason for this is based on a hybrid of conspiracy theories. One concerns the Ionospheric

Research Instrument of the High Frequency Active Auroral Research Program (HAARP) in Alaska. It is credited with (amongst other things) the ability to cause earthquakes, to modify the weather, and to be used for mind control. In reality, it can only cause localised heating of the ionosphere. The conspiracy theory has expanded to engulf any facility, such as an MST radar, that looks similar to the HAARP one. A second conspiracy theory relates to persistent contrails from aircraft, which are referred to as “chem-trails”. Their longevity is interpreted as evidence of them being composed of chemical or biological agents that are sprayed from aircraft for malevolent purposes. In reality it is simply an indication of the high relative humidity of the surrounding air. This conspiracy theory is surprisingly widely believed. One of the more-commonly accepted malevolent purposes is climate modification.

Over 140 people signed up to attend the protest through a Facebook event page. Some had posted messages suggesting that they would like to destroy the radar. However, only 5 people actually turned up and their intentions appear to have been peaceful. They have posted several videos of their visit on YouTube. NERC had advised DAH not to try to engage with the protesters through their Facebook page. This appears to have been good advice as they were unwilling to listen to anyone who tried to argue that the radar was a benign atmospheric research facility, see e.g. <https://www.metabunk.org/threads/the-nerc-funded-mst-radar-facility-in-wales-is-not-a-haarp-installation.3158/>. Nevertheless, DAH was surprised that no-one tried to contact him with their accusations. JMT reported that the Met Office have been targeted by similar groups on several occasions. These protests take the form of a few individuals handing out leaflets at the Met Office's gates. GV advised DAH to remain vigilant in case the MST Radar is targeted again in the future.

ACTION ITEM 53.3.2 DAH to review security measures for the MST Radar site and to make improvements where necessary.

NEW

4. NERC Instrument Report - DAH

Full details of instrument performance issues can be found at http://mst.nerc.ac.uk/cgi-bin/mstlog_public/mst_event_search.py.

4a) Campbell Scientific surface met sensors

The tipping bucket rain gauge is thought to have been partially blocked on 10th May 2014. It recorded only 3 tips for the whole day whilst the WXT510 indicated a moderate accumulation. LD cleaned it out on 13th May although he accidentally re-assembled the unit with the inlet pointing in the wrong direction. Consequently it did not register the rain seen by the WXT510 on 23rd, 24th, and 25th May 2014. LD adjusted the mechanism at around 10 UT on 30th May 2014 and poured a large volume of water into it in order to establish whether it was working correctly.

JMT suggested that maybe real-time rainfall radar data could be used to flag whether or not the tipping bucket rain gauge was operating correctly. DAH pointed out that the nearest rainfall radar was a long way from Aberystwyth and that the mountains of mid Wales blocked it from detecting precipitation at the lowest elevations. GV emphasised that files containing false positive precipitation readings, e.g. for 10th May 2014, should be removed from the BADC. CFL pointed out that although details of unreliable instrument performance were contained in the log, it was time-consuming to read through this when analysing long periods of data. It would be better to have the information available in a machine-readable format. GAP clarified that the BADC already has established procedures for dealing with released data files that need to be corrected. Moreover, they are currently looking into the possibility of annotating data sets. This could be used to append retrospectively-determined reliability details to existing files.

ACTION ITEM 53.4.1 GAP and DAH to remove from the BADC all data files that are known to contain erroneous data.

NEW

ACTION ITEM 53.4.2 GAP and DAH to determine a way of providing retrospectively-determined data reliability details in a machine-readable format.

NEW

4b) Campbell Scientific surface wind sensors

The raw data files contain zeros in all data fields (apart from those for date and time) for the majority of the period between 18:20 UT on 14th February and 05:21 UT 21st February 2014. LD checked the equipment on the 18th and ruled out the possibility of a bad sensor connection. Consequently DAH re-uploaded the acquisition program, on the 18th and again on the 19th, thinking that it might have been lost during a power cut. Realistic-looking values started to be recorded again on the 21st without any other action having been taken. Consequently, it's not known what caused or cured the problem.

DAH noticed several instances, particularly during June 2014, when the raw data files briefly contained zeros in all data fields. The most noticeable case was on 28th May 2014. Although he initially thought that this was a repeat of the problem seen during February, he now thinks that these periods were simply characterised by negligible wind speeds. JP reported that the anemometers used at Cardington also had issues when the wind speed dropped below 3 or 4 m s⁻¹.

4c) Vaisala WXT510 surface met and wind sensors

There is a known bug in the software that is used to create the daily WXT510 netCDF files for the BADC. The software crashes whenever there is a gap in the raw data. There were a significant number of days during the past winter when this problem was encountered. The first occurred on 29th November 2013. There were then 5 days during December 2013 and a further 9 days between 13th and 24th January 2014. The cause of the problems turned out to a failure of one of the disks in the RAID drive of the acquisition PC "julius". This also caused a few timing problems for the MST radar control and data acquisition software (see section 4g), which gave DAH a clue as to the underlying problem. The failed disk was remotely deactivated on 30th January and replaced during DAH's next visit to the radar site on 26th March 2014.

The data acquisition software crashed on the afternoon of 30th December 2013. This was also probably the result of the RAID drive problem since it coincided with a separate MST radar problem (see section 4g). DAH did not spot the problem until 6th January 2014.

4d) Vaisala LD40 laser ceilometer

There are two gaps in the recorded data: between 30th March and 2nd April 2014 and between 17th and 18th June 2014. In both cases the acquisition software on PC "gaius" had shut down unexpectedly.

4e) Sky-camera

The camera remains out of action since it cannot be reached by any of the ladders on site. During the last week of July 2014, DAH will be supervising a work experience student, who will continue the work of creating an event log from the existing images.

4f) Noctilucent Cloud (NLC) Camera

NLCs have been photographed by the camera at Chilbolton on a number of occasions this season. They were observed during dusk on 3rd July 2014 and during the dawn on 10th June and on 3rd, 4th, and 7th July 2014.

4g) MST Radar

LJD began by presenting the monitoring statistics for the past year. EUCOS statistics are derived from comparisons made against the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) model. Met Office statistics are derived from comparisons made against their UKV (1.5 km grid) model. There was a step increase (of approximately 10%) in the daily EUCOS observation count around the beginning of June 2014. The reason for this is not known. Daily EUCOS mean vector difference values were largest between November 2013 and March 2014 (probably as a result of predominant jet stream activity during these months), but only exceeded the maximum target value of 5 m s^{-1} on a few occasions. The daily Root Mean Square (RMS) speed differences show a similar pattern, but the values never exceeded 5 m s^{-1} . The daily RMS direction differences are quite variable. DAH speculated that this could be at least partly the result of inertia gravity wave activity, which modulates both speed and direction in the lower stratosphere. A particularly clear example can be seen during the first 12 hours of 22nd May 2014. He also thinks that this was the cause of "*suspicious speed/direction values during 0130-0330 UT for $z \sim 12 \text{ km}$ on the 3rd of June [2014]*" that the E-PROFILE network manager had brought to his attention. Availability and Timeliness values were good for all months except January 2014, when they dipped slightly. The Met Office's statistics continue to show a slight positive speed bias for tropospheric altitudes and a slight negative one for stratospheric altitudes. The RMS speed and direction differences remain consistently low.

DAH presented the rest of this section. There have been no major problems with the radar since the last meeting although there have been a large number of minor ones. The transmitter for antenna sector A (TXA) suffered from a blown fuse on one occasion and shut down with an analogue error on another occasion (albeit several times during a single day). Although it is necessary for LD to be on site in order to replace a blown fuse, DAH can remotely restart a transmitter that has encountered an analogue error. TXB suffered from a blown fuse on 7 occasions and encountered analogue errors on 11 occasions. The latter were clustered within the period 25th March - 3rd April 2014. LD installed a new voltage regulator on 9th April 2014 and the problem has not occurred since. TXC suffered a blown fuse on 4 occasions. TXD has not encountered any problems. TXE suffered from a blown fuse on one occasion.

There have also been several minor issues associated with the beam steering units. Units 41, 42, 51, and 52, which are fed from the same final power divider, became unresponsive on 9th January 2014 and on 7th and 11th February 2014. In each case they reverted to an operational status without any intervention having been taken. Unit 95 became unresponsive on 9 separate occasions on 12th January 2014. It was replaced by a spare unit on 21st January 2014 after it became unresponsive again during the early hours of that morning. Unit 35 became unresponsive for 3 hours on 27th March 2014 and again for an hour on the following day. No intervention was taken. Unit 37 indicated high Voltage Standing Wave Ratio (VSWR) values on 8th May 2014. LD replaced it on the following day and found that one of its coils had become loose. It was put back into service on 13th May 2014 after being repaired.

As mentioned in section 4c, the PC ("julius") on which the radar control and data acquisition software runs developed a RAID disk problem in late 2013. This is thought to have been the underlying cause of the unusually long intervals of 7 and 20 minutes between two sets of dwells in a single cycle of observation on 30th December 2013. The typical interval is just 26 s. Moreover, the spectral files for this cycle were causing the signal processing software on PC "claudius" to crash. DAH solved the latter problem by deleting the files in question. Single instances of unusually long dwell intervals were also seen on 24th and 29th January 2014. The failed disk was removed from service on 30th January 2014.

The socket between the radar control PC and the beam steering PC was unexpectedly broken on 3rd April 2014. It seems likely that this was a result of the simultaneous 4 minute long input power problem (see section 3c). There was a gap of 200 s whilst the radar control PC made repeated efforts to reconnect. The operation of the radar does not appear to have been otherwise affected.

Based on an analysis of satellite, MST radar, and surface meteorological data, GAP suspects that a Sting Jet passed over Aberystwyth on 12th February 2014. MST radar wind speeds of up to 50 m s^{-1} were seen between altitudes of 2 and 6 km and between times of 14:30 and 18:00 UT. The corresponding 15 minute mean Frongoch surface wind speeds of 20 m s^{-1} suggest that the jet had not reached ground level at this latitude. However, gust speeds of nearly 50 m s^{-1} were reported for the Llyn Peninsula, which is approximately 50 km to the north.

5. Guest Instrument Report

GV reported that the boundary-layer wind-profiler (BLWP) is currently at Cardington and working well. The Elight lidar has suffered from power problems, which have yet to be resolved. A new laser for the water vapour lidar was originally used with the wrong polarisation. Now that this has been corrected the instrument is giving good results. Someone is currently writing software to allow useful data products to be extracted automatically from the observations. A summer student has been examining the observations made during volcanic ash episodes. At that time, quick look plots were e-mailed to the Met Office on an ad hoc basis. GV assumes that, in the event of another episode, the Met Office will require numerical data products to be delivered in a standard way. There is currently no mechanism for doing this. However, at the end of the current project he should at least have a good idea of which data products might be useful. JMT reported that the Met Office have now procured the new lidars that are capable of detecting volcanic ash.

6. Science and technical presentations

6a) Background information for the LANFEX field campaign - JP

Fog is a high-impact meteorological phenomenon and so there is a need to be able to forecast it accurately. Nevertheless, this remains a challenge for numerical weather prediction models. For example, on radiatively-cooled nights, fog doesn't always form despite very high relative humidities ($> 98\%$) persisting for long periods; the vertical motions associated with convective and stratiform clouds would ensure that saturation occurs under such circumstances. Moreover, it is not known why fog formation can be so spatially inhomogeneous or what causes fog to spread rapidly. The effect of orography is poorly-understood and the importance of mixing and turbulence needs to be better quantified.

The Local And Non Local Fog EXperiment (LANFEX), which will be run between Autumn 2014 and Spring 2016, is designed to address these issues. Networks of instruments will be operated both at the Met Office's Cardington site and in the vicinity of the Clun valley, which is close to the Welsh/English border. The equipment will include surface flux stations, dew deposition meters, a tethered balloon system, radiosondes, infra-red imaging cameras, and a Halo Doppler lidar. A recently-developed unmanned aerial system will be used to map temperature and humidity patterns at low levels during the evening transition. The experiment will be closely tied to modelling studies.

6b) Update on volcanic ash detection using lidars at Capel Dewi in recent years - HMAR

The VANAHEIM (Volcanic and Atmospheric Near- to far-field Analysis of plumes Helping Interpretation and Modelling) consortium was set up following the Eyjafjallajökull eruption of 2010. Its aim is to improve the prediction of ash plume dispersal. Instruments that are capable of remotely sensing ash particles clearly play an important role in achieving this.

The water vapour lidar at Capel Dewi provides extinction and backscatter coefficients. The Elight ozone and aerosol lidar provides a backscatter coefficient. These two sets of data have to be combined in order to derive the depolarisation ratio, which is used to infer the presence of ash particles. At the time of the 2010 eruption, quick-look plots from the different lidar systems were made available through a web site. Although this was useful, the Met Office will require quantitative products in near-real-time in order to make informed decisions involving any future ash plumes. Software is currently being developed for

this purpose. It is being tested on observations made during the 2010 eruption. JMT commented that data from the Met Office's new lidars will feed into the existing lidarnet network.

6c) Impact of wind-profilers versus other observing systems seen by FSO and impact evaluated using denial experiment - CG

The Forecast Sensitivity to Observations (FSO) tool measures the change in Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) forecast error (i.e. the difference between the forecast and the analysis fields) associated with observational inputs. It is highly versatile and can, for example, be used to consider the impact of a single instrument, of a group of instruments, or of observations at a particular level. Three different periods have been considered: one month in late summer 2010, two months in early 2012, and four months in spring 2013. The results are from the global model, which uses 4Dvar assimilation and a six hour window. The impact is taken as the reduction in forecast error at 24 hours over the entire atmosphere.

Since the tool has only recently been developed, the current results need to be treated with some caution. For example, any variability in impact could depend on the validity of the assumptions of the tool, the assimilation technique used, or the particular weather conditions encountered, as well as the quality of the input data. Nevertheless, the Japanese wind-profilers (WPs) consistently show a positive impact. The results for the US profilers are more variable between individual instruments and between test periods. Attention has been focused on the WP at Cena in Alaska. The impact for 2010 was predominantly positive below 5 km but negative above. It is possible that this was the result of missing data points at the higher altitudes. The assimilation scheme treated WP data like radiosonde data and so linear interpolation was used in the vertical to fill data gaps. This is not always appropriate, e.g. when the missing values occur at the altitude of the jet peak. The assimilation code had been changed in order to reduce this problem by the time of the 2012 test period. The corresponding FSO results show positive impact for virtually all heights.

The relative impacts of radiosondes and WPs, for Germany and the UK, have been compared. Although radiosondes have a higher positive impact per profile than WPs, the latter provide many more profiles per day. The 4Dvar system appears to benefit from hourly WP inputs and the accumulated impact is slightly more positive than that for radiosondes. The Aberystwyth radar had only a moderate impact for the 2010 period, i.e. before the 2011 renovation. However, it was amongst the WPs with the most positive impact for the 2013 period. It's not clear whether the reduced impact for the South Uist WP over the same period was a result of system degradation. The radar has recently been renovated.

6d) Data denial experiment in Met Office high resolution NWP model - ZL

The Met Office has developed an NWP-based nowcasting system - the Nowcasting Demonstration Project (NDP) - with the aim of producing more-accurate and timely forecasts of high-impact weather events. A 4Dvar system assimilates sub-hourly data and produces forecasts for every hour out to T+6 hours. It was run in real time between March 2012 and March 2013. Some data products were updated every 10 or 15 minutes, e.g. WP data, weather radar radial winds, and some of the channels from the MSG SEVIRI satellite instrument. Others were updated every hour, e.g. MSG cloud- and humidity-tracked winds, aircraft temperature and winds, and surface meteorological data.

A data denial experiment was carried out in order to evaluate the impact of WP input (from the Camborne, Dunkeswell, and Wattisham BLWPs and from the Aberystwyth MST Radar) for forecasting precipitation in connection with 5 flooding events from 2012. Fractions skill scores were used to quantify the agreement between the forecast and the (weather radar) observed fields over different-sized sampling areas. The latter are referred to in terms of neighbourhood lengths. Control runs were compared with those for which WP data had been excluded. The control runs had smaller neighbourhood lengths for the same skill at the same forecast time. They also had shorter lead times for the same skill at the same neighbourhood size. Both of these indicate the positive impact of assimilating WP data.

6e) Evaluation of wind profiles from the NCAS boundary-layer wind-profiler - CFL

CFL had previously compared winds derived from the MST radar with those derived from radiosondes (see section 6b of the previous meeting's minutes). The original aim had been to quantify the uncertainty in the radar-derived winds for turbulence studies. However, the analysis led to a surprising result. The profiles of the mean difference between the radar and radiosonde wind speeds and of the mean radar-derived vertical velocity had similar "S" shapes. This has been attributed to the effects of mountain waves. It is thought that the horizontal separation between the radar and radiosonde measurements leads to different phases of the waves being sampled. A paper on this work was submitted to Atmospheric Measurement Techniques in March 2014.

CFL has now turned his attention to examining the winds measured by the NCAS BLWP. He has analysed data from a period when the BLWP was operated alongside a sodar (i.e. an acoustic WP) at the Weybourne field site. The surrounding landscape is flat and so mountain wave activity can be discounted. The (time) mean vertical velocities for BLWP observations are slightly negative and more-negative than the values for sodar observations. This is consistent with what has already been reported in the literature. The difference between the profiles is much smaller for BLWP Doppler spectra with a velocity bin interval of 0.12 m s^{-1} than for those with an interval of 0.31 m s^{-1} (the width of the spectra and the interval between velocity bins are automatically adapted to accommodate the largest-magnitude Doppler shifts). This difference might be a result of ground clutter removal, which blanks the central velocity bins and so could bias the radial velocities of near-zero Doppler shift signals to larger magnitudes. CG suggested that this hypothesis could be tested further by examining the distribution of vertical velocities and looking for a notch around 0.0 m s^{-1} .

CFL has also compared the profiles of the mean vertical velocities from the BLWP with those from the MST radar. They are similar in shape (indicative of mountain wave activity) and show a change from positive to negative values at the same altitude. However, the BLWP values are larger in magnitude. The best fit lines between BLWP and radiosonde horizontal wind speeds have gradients of approximately 0.9, indicating that the BLWP underestimates wind speeds compared with those measured by radiosondes. A similar pattern is seen when comparing BLWP and MST radar horizontal wind speeds. The difference between the values depends on speed rather than altitude. One possible cause of the BLWP underestimating wind speeds is that its off-vertical beam antennas are slightly mis-aligned. Finally CFL has tried projecting the uncertainty in horizontal winds into the radial directions. The values are approximately constant as a function of height and are slightly lower for dry compared to precipitation conditions.

6f) The optimal level of time averaging for MST Radar winds - DAH

DAH gave an update on the work that he had presented in section 6a of the previous meeting. He had demonstrated that time averaging should be applied to MST Radar winds in order to improve their accuracy. The perturbations of single cycle estimates from the 5 cycle mean can be as large as $\pm 10 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ for mean speeds of 50 m s^{-1} . The interval between standard cycles of observation is 5 minutes 14 seconds. In order to objectively determine the optimal level of time averaging, the mean magnitude of the wind vector change in time is evaluated. This represents a combination of the random measurement error and of the natural variability of the wind. The change is evaluated over the same interval as was used for averaging. The predominant effect of low levels of averaging is to reduce the random error. The natural variability begins to dominate for longer intervals. Consequently, the optimal level of averaging can be taken as that at which the mean magnitude of the change reaches a minimum value.

At the time of the last Experimenters' meeting, DAH had performed this analysis for a year's worth of data, albeit considering mean values on a daily basis. The natural variability of the wind tends to be localised rather than uniformly distributed in time. Consequently the values varied somewhat from day to day. DAH has now repeated the analysis taking the mean values over the entire year. The minimum value occurs at 6 cycle averaging (31.5 minutes) for the troposphere. This corresponds closely to the 30

minute averaging currently used for the data delivered to the Met Office. However, for the stratosphere the mean value continues to decrease up to 11 cycle averaging (57.6 minutes), the longest interval considered so far. Owing to the abrupt transition between tropospheric and stratospheric behaviour, DAH suspects that the step increase in static stability is somehow responsible.

GV stressed that he was primarily interested in the aspect sensitivity compensation aspects of this work. He pointed out that a number of action items were being held whilst this investigation was ongoing. He was of the opinion that climatological mean values would be more appropriate than locally-evaluated ones. The onus was on DAH to demonstrate that the opposite was true. CFL suggested that the compensation factor might be more reliable if a 2nd 4.2° beam dwell were added to each cycle of observation.

6g) Wind-profiler backscatter monitoring against UKV - CG and ZL

The clear-air backscatter power observed by WPs depends on the vertical gradient of potential refractive index. Since the latter depends on both temperature and humidity (gradients), which are important weather forecast parameters, it would be useful to be able to assimilate the information. The fact that the data from the BLWPs are available at intervals of just 15 minutes in time and 75 m in altitude make this particularly significant for the high-resolution UKV model. The aim of this work is to establish whether the additional data might be useful. Attention will initially be focused on the Camborne and Wattisham BLWPs since they are colocated with laser ceilometers. The latter can be used to establish when the sky is clear and therefore when the possibility of hydrometeor scatter can be discounted. In the case of the Aberystwyth and South Uist MST radars, the aspect sensitivity parameter will be needed in order to determine whether an isotropic or non-isotropic backscatter model is required.

7. Any Other Business

The date of the next Experimenters' meeting was provisionally set for January 2015.